

EFFECT OF BOILING AND FRYING ON THE ENZYMIC HYDROLYSIS OF FISH PROTEIN.

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The effects of different methods of cooking, frying and boiling, for different periods of time on the enzyme hydrolysis of the proteins of fish have been studied. The hydrolysis has been carried out *in vitro* by pepsin, trypsin and by pepsin followed by trypsin. The rate of digestion of fish under-cooked in boiling water is greater than that of raw, fried or thoroughly cooked fish. With all the species under investigation, the rate of hydrolysis is found to be greater in peptic digestion than in tryptic, except in two cases viz. Boal (*Wallagu attu*) and Shole (*Ophcephalus strattus*) where the results are reversed.

From the nutritional standpoint the art of cooking and its effects on the digestibility and nutritive value of foodstuffs constitute an important problem. According to Hutchinson ("Food and Principles of Dietetics", p. 396), cooking increases the digestibility of vegetable foodstuffs, but decreases that of animal foodstuffs. Heinbecker (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1928, 80, 462) states that the Eskimo in his native condition eats practically raw flesh and remains healthy. But in those parts, where owing to the spread of civilisation, the Eskimo cooks his meat, health has deteriorated and scurvy occurs. Much work on the effect of cooking on the nutritive value of foodstuffs has been carried out in England by McCance and co-workers.

In the present work the effects of different methods of cooking, frying and boiling for different periods of time on the digestibility of the proteins of fish, which constitutes an important article of diet in Bengal, have been investigated. The digestions have been carried out *in vitro* by pepsin, trypsin and by pepsin followed by trypsin.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The edible portions of the fresh fish samples, purchased from the local market, were cut into small and equal pieces. Each of the pieces from the same part of the body of the same fish was divided into 4 equal portions in order to maintain uniformity as far as possible. Of these four samples (a) one was kept raw, (b) one was fried in mustard oil till the colour of the fish was dark brown, as is done in the domestic kitchen in Bengal, (c) one was cooked for 20 minutes in boiling water and (d) one was under-cooked in boiling water for 10 minutes. These are referred to as raw, fried, cooked and under-cooked respectively in the tables which give the averages of the determinations of three samples in each case. After cooking the pieces were allowed to cool, any obvious fat and connective tissue were removed and the remaining portion was minced in an 'Enterprise' mincer before digestion.

Peptic Digestion.—The following experiments were carried out with (a) 75 g. of raw fish, (b) 75 g. of raw fish after frying, (c) 75 g. of raw fish after boiling for 20 minutes and (d) 75 g. of raw fish after boiling for 10 minutes. 75 G. of the tissue were treated with 75 c.c. of distilled water and left in a refrigerator overnight. Next day the p_{H} of the medium was adjusted to 2.0 with the addition of hydrochloric acid and the flask kept in a thermostat at 40° for half an hour. 10 C.c. of a 10% pepsin solution (Merck's) were then added to the mixture and the mixture incubated for 3 hours. 10 C.c. of the mixture were withdrawn from time to time and added to 50 c.c. of 95% alcohol and titrated with *N/25* alcoholic caustic potash solution by means of a micro-burette (Wiilstätter's method). Each time a blank experiment was made by just adding the enzyme to the substrate and titrating immediately. Results are given in Table I.

TABLE I.

Bengali name.	Zoological name.	Time of digestion.	No. of c.c. of <i>N/25</i> alcoholic KOH.			
			Raw.	Fried.	Cooked.	Under-cooked.
			(a)	(b)	(c)	(d)
Rohu	<i>Labeo rohita</i>	60 min.	0.76	0.68	0.77	1.20
		120	1.40	0.82	0.92	1.45
		180	1.56	1.20	1.32	1.63
Hilsha	<i>Clupea tilsa</i>	60	1.30	0.86	0.96	1.28
		120	1.65	1.21	1.35	1.63
		180	1.72	1.52	1.62	1.84
Shinghi	<i>Saccobranchus fossilis</i>	60	1.25	0.92	0.88	1.31
		120	1.69	1.05	1.23	1.70
		180	1.88	1.34	1.45	1.92
Koi	<i>Anabas testudineus</i>	60	1.30	0.98	1.25	1.45
		120	1.62	1.25	1.38	1.54
		180	1.72	1.45	1.52	1.83
Mrigal	<i>Cirrhina mrigala</i>	60	0.82	0.73	0.81	0.96
		120	1.20	0.88	1.15	1.21
		180	1.49	1.16	1.35	1.43
Kalbasu	<i>Labeo calbasu</i>	60	0.82	0.73	0.81	0.96
		120	1.20	0.88	1.15	1.21
		180	1.49	1.16	1.35	1.52
Tengra	—	60	0.92	0.72	0.75	0.73
		120	1.10	0.96	0.96	1.10
		180	1.35	1.28	1.32	1.65
Parshey	<i>Mugil persia</i>	60	1.10	0.82	1.12	1.21
		120	1.30	1.25	1.26	1.36
		180	1.73	1.55	1.63	1.80
Boal	<i>Wallago attu</i>	60	0.66	0.55	0.62	0.78
		120	0.89	0.78	0.91	0.96
		180	1.30	0.97	1.21	1.38
Shole	<i>Ophcephalus striatus</i>	60	0.95	0.75	0.72	1.15
		120	1.20	1.20	1.01	1.26
		180	1.63	1.50	1.52	1.72

Tryptic Digestion.—In these experiments 10 c.c. of a 10% solution of activated trypsin were added to 75 g. of the minced tissue (which had been heated with 75 c.c. of distilled water at 40° for half an hour) after adjusting the p_H of the medium to 8.5 by means of caustic potash solution. The determination of tryptic hydrolysis was carried out in the same way as in peptic digestion. In these experiments also a preliminary blank experiment was carried out in each case. Results are given in Table II.

The trypsin used was activated by means of cystine in the following way before use. 10 G. of trypsin (Merck) were placed in a 100 c.c. measuring flask with 50 c.c. of water, 5 c.c. of phosphate buffer ($M/15$) at p_H 8.5

TABLE II.

Digestibility of fish protein with activated trypsin.

Bengali name.	Zoological name.	Time of digestion	No. of c.c. of $N/25$ alcoholic KOH.			
			Raw. (a)	Fried. (b)	Cooked. (c)	Under-cooked. (d)
Rohu	<i>Labeo rohita</i>	60 minute	0.54	0.53	0.62	1.00
		120	0.96	0.82	0.77	1.21
		180	1.23	1.03	1.28	1.35
Hilsha	<i>Clupea litsea</i>	60	1.20	0.72	0.83	1.20
		120	1.42	1.11	1.25	1.53
		180	1.53	1.50	1.58	1.62
Shinghi	<i>Saccobranchus fossilis</i>	60	1.20	0.92	0.82	1.25
		120	1.42	1.15	1.20	1.53
		180	1.63	1.30	1.44	1.68
Koi	<i>Anabas testudineus</i>	60	1.10	0.88	0.82	1.12
		120	1.26	1.01	1.25	1.23
		180	1.52	1.43	1.48	1.64
Mrigal	<i>Cirrhina mrigala</i>	60	0.65	0.62	0.63	0.74
		120	0.83	0.78	0.92	1.20
		180	1.36	1.25	1.32	1.42
Kalbasu	<i>Labeo kalbasu</i>	60	0.53	0.50	0.63	0.66
		120	0.84	0.73	0.79	0.96
		180	1.20	1.06	1.16	1.42
Tengra	—	60	0.83	0.66	0.70	0.84
		120	1.02	0.96	0.86	1.12
		180	1.25	1.17	1.29	1.63
Parshey	<i>Mugil parsia</i>	60	0.84	0.62	0.91	1.12
		120	1.02	0.73	1.20	1.31
		180	1.25	1.20	1.33	1.45
Boal	<i>Wallago attu</i>	60	1.25	1.10	1.26	1.20
		120	1.39	1.28	1.42	1.58
		180	1.52	1.48	1.56	1.63
Shole	<i>Ophcephalus striatus</i>	60	1.01	0.86	0.88	1.21
		120	1.26	1.20	1.36	1.38
		180	1.73	1.43	1.81	1.88

TABLE III.

Digestibility of fish protein with pepsin and trypsin.

Bengali name.	Zoological name.	Time of digestion.	No. of c.c. of N/25 alcoholic KOH			
			Raw. (a)	Fried. (b)	Cooked. (c)	Under-cooked. (d)
Rohu	<i>Labeo rohita</i>	60 min.	1.20	1.13	1.25	1.36
		120	1.82	1.46	1.53	1.92
Hilsha	<i>Clupea tilisa</i>	60	1.52	1.10	1.00	1.21
		120	1.65	1.32	1.43	1.82
Shinghi	<i>Saccobranchus fossilis</i>	60	1.33	1.21	1.30	1.52
		120	1.78	1.43	1.63	1.84
Koi	<i>Anabas testudineus</i>	60	1.52	1.22	1.38	1.61
		120	1.82	1.52	1.76	1.86
Mrigal	<i>Cirrhina mrigala</i>	60	1.20	0.92	1.21	1.31
		120	1.55	1.32	1.43	1.78
Kalbasu	<i>Labeo calbasu</i>	60	1.21	0.89	1.15	1.41
		120	1.53	1.28	1.48	1.63
Tengra	—	60	1.62	1.38	1.52	1.73
		120	1.85	1.45	1.68	1.93
Parshey	<i>Mugil parsia</i>	60	1.21	1.12	1.22	1.36
		120	1.65	1.42	1.53	1.68
Boal	<i>Wallago attu</i>	60	0.92	0.82	0.76	1.35
		120	1.46	1.20	1.36	1.72
Shole	<i>Ophcephalus striatus</i>	60	1.22	1.10	0.99	1.33
		120	1.69	1.28	1.43	1.96

and 5 c.c. of 0.005M cystine solution at p_H 8.5 (Grassmann, *Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1930, 186, 183). The flask was then kept in a thermostat for 30 minutes at 40°. The volume of the solution was made upto 100 c.c. with the addition of water heated to 40°.

Combined Action of Pepsin and Trypsin.—Fish (75 g. raw or after treatment) was treated with 75 c.c. of distilled water and the p_H of the mixture adjusted to 2.0 with hydrochloric acid. Pepsin (10%, 10 c.c.) was added in each of the flasks, which were incubated for 3 hours at 40°. The mixtures were then neutralised with caustic potash solution and the p_H was adjusted to 8.5 and treated with activated trypsin as described above. Results are shown in Table III.

DISCUSSION.

From the foregoing results it appears that the rate of digestion varies from species to species which is apparently connected with differences in the

composition of the proteins of the fish. The rate of digestion of fish undercooked in boiling water is greater than that of raw, fried or thoroughly cooked fish. This may be due to possible destruction of anti-enzymic properties in the under-cooked fish, while the proteins at this stage are not markedly denatured, which might have hindered the rate of hydrolysis. These findings are in agreement with those of Clifford (*Biochem. J.*, 1930 **24**, 1729) who states that overcooked meat is very slowly digested as compared with underdone meat and the maximum rate of digestion is obtained with the latter. With all the species under investigation the rate of hydrolysis is found to be greater in peptic digestion than in the tryptic except in the cases of *Boal* (*Wallage attu*) and *Shole* (*Ophcephalus striatus*) where the results are reversed. When peptic digestion is followed by tryptic digestion hydrolysis is more complete than in the case of pepsin or trypsin alone. The results would indicate that in the normal process of digestion *in vivo*, the break-down of fish proteins would be fairly complete. But, as indicated above, in general the digestibility is the greatest with underdone fish as compared with raw, fully cooked or fried fish. In the case of the last two, digestibility is obviously impaired by denaturation, hardening and drying of the proteins.

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